

Đồng Dương Temple

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The 9th century Đồng Dương monastery consisted of structures with long hallways and rectangular enclosures. The brick monastery has three sections: the vihara, long hallway, and main shrine. The monastery was built with corbel roofs, which significantly darken the interior. Buddhists in Champa belonged to the Mahayana and Tantric order, focusing on observations of the cult of the Buddha and Avalokiteshvara.

Date Range: 900 CE - 1000 CE

Region: Đồng Dương, present-day Bình Định, Vietnam

Region tags: Vietnam, Southeast Asia, Central Vietnam

Attached maps include Champa in 9th - 10th century. The polygon is the approximate location of the Đồng Dương Monastery itself.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Protor, Ann R. "Buddhist Art of 9th century Champa: Đồng Dương." Ed. Kim, David W. *Colonial Transformation and Asian Religions in Modern History*, Newcastle upon Tyne, UK: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2018, p. 140-162
- Source 2: Dhar, Parul Pandya. "Buddhism, Art and Ritual Practice: Dong Duong at the Intersection of Asian Cultures." *Asian Encounters: Exploring Connected Histories*, edited by Upinder Singh and Parul Pandya Dhar, Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2014, p. 111-136 and Figs. 6.1-6.16
- Source 3: Chau, Mya. "Interrelationships in South and Southeast Asian Art: Cham Female Iconography, Buddhist Inscriptions and the Buddha Image," *Explorations: a Graduate Student Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, Fall, Volume 12, 2014, p. 12-31

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

- Source 1: Chutiwongs, Nandana. "Le Bouddhisme du Champa." *Tresors d'art du Vietnam: la sculpture du Champa V-XV siècle*. Guimet musee national des arts asiatiques, 12 octobre 2005- 9 janvier 2006, p.

65-87

- Source 2: Nguyen, Trian. "Laksmindralokesvara, main Deity of the Dong-Duong Monastery: A masterpiece of Cham art and a new interpretation." *Artibus Asiae*, no 1. 1995, p. 5-38
- Source 3: Mabbett, Ian. "Buddhism in Champa." *Southeast Asia in the 9th to 14th Centuries*. Marr, D G and Milner, A C (eds.), Singapore: Institute for Southeast Asian Studies and Canberra: Research School of Pacific Studies, Australian National University, 1986, p. 289-313

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://journals.openedition.org/moussons/810>
- Source 1 Description: Buddhism in Ćampā, Le Bouddhisme au Champa, by Anne-Valérie Schweyer
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Dong-Duong>
- Source 2 Description: Đồng Dương temple, encyclopedia entry

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1902-4

Notes: Henri Parmentier and Charles Carpeau conducted excavations near the northeast tower at Đồng Dương monastery, Quang Nam province.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: EFEO French excavations during 1902-4.

Specific to this answer:

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Type of elevation

– Hill

– Mountain

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Type of feature

– Mound

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Water feature

– Plantings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
 - Rectangular

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

- ↳ One single feature
 - Clearing

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

- For religious reasons
- For political reasons
- As the result of war
- As the result of pillage

Notes: Đổng Dương complex was most likely devastated by invasions and looting expeditions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

- Natural phenomena

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ In antiquity

- More than once

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ In modernity

- Post-Renaissance

Notes: Archaeologists have tried to reconstruct the Đổng Dương temple with drawings and what it might have looked like inside.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Laksmindra-Lokesvara

Notes: Sanskrit inscriptions reveal that the monastery honored the king's personal deity, Laksmindra-Lokesvara. His personal deity represented a triad; the goddess Laksmi, the bodhisattva Avalokitesvara, and the king Indravarman II, himself.

Specific to this answer:

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Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: The king followed an established tradition by linking his name to that of his patron deity, symbolizing the king's absorption with the divine.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: All of the above: Thanksgiving to the gods, expectation of favor in return, and expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The principal sanctuary was the most important component of the monastery, with nine smaller shrines that surrounded the central tower.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 70

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 1500

Notes: 1.5 kilometers (.9 mile) from east to west.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 1.5

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1500

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 1.5

Notes: The largest sandstone Buddha found in Đồng Dương temple stood at the height of 5 foot.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Earth

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Grass
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Brick

Specific to this answer:
Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Paint

Specific to this answer:
Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: localized Cham symbols and iconography

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: A large stone pedestal with an altar sits at the end of the main sanctuary.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Buddha, Bodhisattvas, Devas, Goddesses,

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Worshippers

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Statues of local goddesses

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: reliefs representing the animal world: elephants

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Inscriptions written in Cham recorded legal details such as land donations and practical details like the dimensions of land.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Cham local motifs

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: A statue of a Cham goddess have been found fifty meters from the monastery's main sanctuary. Art historians have argued that the eyes of have been re-cut and stylized with Cham-likeness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Humans

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Human narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Animals

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Are they gender specific: Yes. There is a strong presence of the feminine divine as a supreme high god.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: medicinal herbs

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: through ancestor practice and worship

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: through worship

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: medicinal herbs

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: There are hidden deposits underneath and inside the temple.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Rice and fruit

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:
– Yes [specify]: Gold plaques of gods

↳ Daily life objects:
– No

↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: Incenses, perfumes, and sacred water

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: supernatural beings care about temple building and image/inscription donations

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

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Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: material offerings placed as sacred deposits under the temple

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

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Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Buddhist monks and worshippers

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: The architecture of the Đồng Dương temple has been largely destroyed due to bombing and abandonment of the site during the Vietnam War.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The temple site was abandoned after the decline of Buddhism beginning in the 10th century, Champa

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

- ↳ Priests
 - Yes
- ↳ Local elites
 - Yes
- ↳ Private contributions
 - Yes
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: queens, daughters, and related royal women

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: The plan of the Đồng Dương shows structures with long hallways and rectangular enclosures. The long hallways with allow large gatherings of people that could accommodate activities such as feasting.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: Chinese sources indicate that the Chams participated in annual Buddhist festivals.

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: annual
- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members
 - Elites
- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:
 - No

- ↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: 1000
- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Elites
 - Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

- ↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

 - No
- ↳ Divination through human communication:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:
 - Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:
– Yes

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:
– Yes

↳ Are intoxicants required:
– Yes

↳ Physical ordeal required:
– Yes

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:
– Smoke
– Flame

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: divination through living material: statues were thought to be "alive" and possessed sacred spirits of the divine

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation
– No

↳ Healing magic
– Yes

↳ Cleansing
– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Blessing rituals

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 1000

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Records indicate annually or in correspondence to the ritual calendar

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Present full time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Present part time

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Function for water management:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: place for worship

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Central and Southern Vietnam

Bibliography

General References

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